

THE SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITIES OF SHONAZAR SHOABDURAHMONOV

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ABSTRACT

Throughout his academic career, Academician Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov conducted research on the language of literary and folklore works, orthography, punctuation, modern Uzbek language, dialectology, and linguistic geography. This article provides an overview of the scientist's life path and his scientific research in these areas. His contributions to the field of Uzbek philology are highlighted.

Introduction. Shonazar Shoabdurahmonovich Shoabdurahmonov, a prominent linguist who made a significant contribution to the development of Uzbek philology, was born on May 5, 1923, in Tashkent. He was a full member of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, laureate of the Abu Rayhan Beruni State Prize of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor, dedicated researcher, and a generous and devoted person. A year after his birth, his father passed away, and he remained under his mother's care. In 1940, having graduated with honors from a secondary school in Tashkent, he entered the Faculty of Uzbek Language and Literature at the Nizomiy Tashkent State Pedagogical Institute (now Tashkent State Pedagogical University) and graduated with distinction in 1944. To further his knowledge and engage in scientific research, Sh. Shoabdurahmonov pursued postgraduate studies in Uzbek linguistics at the Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 1944 to 1948. The years of postgraduate studies were a great learning experience for Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov. The young researcher benefited from the scientific guidance of the renowned folklorist Hodi Zarifov, the prominent linguist Zokir Ma'rufov, and the eminent Turkologist, Academician Viktor Vasilyevich Reshetov, working tirelessly to expand his knowledge. He became interested in researching the linguistic features of literary works and in 1948 published an article about the language of the poem "Po'lat quyuvchi" (Steelmaker). This was the first published scientific work of Sh. Shoabdurahmonov, who later became a prominent linguist. While pursuing his graduate studies, the future scholar meticulously studied the language of the dastan "Ravshan" from the repertoire of the renowned folk bakhshi Ergash Jumanbulbul o'g'li. In 1949, he completed the monograph "Artistic Features of the Language of the Dastan "Ravshan" and successfully defended it to obtain the degree of Candidate of Philological Sciences. It should be particularly noted that this scientific work by the young linguist was the first monographic study dedicated to a deep scientific examination of the artistic

features in the language of fiction and folklore works. This work was written so meticulously, originally, and meaningfully that, although it was not published as a separate book, it continues to serve as a guiding program for young researchers, postgraduate students, and generally those engaged in Uzbek philology who have studied or are studying the language of literary works from a scientific perspective.

Sh.Shoabdurakhmanov's entire scientific career was closely linked to the Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. He served as a junior researcher in the Uzbek Language Department of this institute from 1949 to 1951, as a senior researcher from 1951 to 1954, as head of the Uzbek Dialectology Department from 1954 to 1991, and as a chief researcher from 1991 to 1998. Throughout his tenure, he conducted extensive scientific research on the distinctive linguistic features of Uzbek folk dialects.

Sh.Shoabdurakhmanov made a significant contribution to the development of philological science in Uzbekistan not only as an accomplished linguist but also as a talented organizer of scientific endeavors. He served as the chairman of the Coordinating Scientific Council on Linguistics at the Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan (1967-84), director of the Institute of Language and Literature (1971-74), member of the main editorial board of the Uzbek Encyclopedia (1971-80), member of the Presidium of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan and academic secretary of the Department of History, Linguistics and Literary Studies (1974-76), chairman of the Joint Scientific Council on Philology at the Department of History, Linguistics and Literary Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan (1974-76), member of the Presidium of the Committee of Turkologists (1974-83), chairman of the specialized scientific council for the defense of doctoral dissertations at the Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan (1976-80), coordinating director of the "Dialectological Atlas of Turkic Peoples" for the Central Asian region (1979-80), and member of the editorial board of the "Uzbek Language and Literature" journal (1966-2009). In these roles, he spearheaded the noble work of creating fundamental scientific research in Uzbek linguistics.

Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov is a comprehensive scholar who has conducted scientific research on various issues in Uzbek linguistics. He has published numerous scientific articles, treatises, dictionaries, and monographs on the linguopoetic features of folklore texts, current problems of the Uzbek language, dialectology, lexicology, lexicography, phonetics, orthography (spelling), and punctuation.

In Sh. Shoabdurahmonov's scientific work, the study of the language of folk epics holds a special place. Through examining the linguistic features of the dastan "Ravshan", he revealed Ergash Jumanbulbul o'g'li's unique artistic skill in utilizing the lexical richness of the folk language. The scholar's articles "Elements of Artistic Phonetics in the Dastan Ravshan" (1967), "Artistic Imagery and Expression in the Dastans of Ergash Jumanbulbul" (1970), "On the Language of Ergash Jumanbulbul's Dastan Ravshan" (1971), and "Folk Wisdom" (1978) express important theoretical views on the poetic nature of Uzbek folklore language.

In the 1950s, when issues of Uzbek orthography and punctuation were actively debated, the scholar gained public recognition with his valuable works in this field. In collaboration with his mentors and colleagues Z.Ma'rufov, T.Shermuhamedov, F.Kamol, and S.Ibrohimov, he

published "Collection of Orthographic Exercises" (reprinted 8 times between 1949-1956) for grades 5 and 6 of seven-year and secondary schools, and "Basic Rules of Uzbek Orthography" (reprinted 5 times between 1952-1956). Additionally, he authored treatises and articles such as "On the Spelling of the Vowels "e" and "i" (1950), "On Some Issues of Uzbek Punctuation" (1952), "Some Questions of Uzbek Punctuation" (in Russian, 1952), "Punctuation Rules" (1953), "Rules of Punctuation" (1952), "Punctuation in the Uzbek Language" (1955), "Learn the Rules of Orthography" (1956), and "Basic Rules of Uzbek Orthography and Punctuation" (1981).

The scholar also made significant contributions to developing textbooks and curricula for secondary schools and higher education institutions, as well as comprehensively illuminating certain aspects of Uzbek grammar in a scientific manner: "Uzbek Language Program" (co-authored, 1952), "Auxiliary Words in the Uzbek Language" (1953), "Phonetics: Materials for the Uzbek Language Course" (co-authored with V. Reshetov, 1953), "Modern Uzbek Language" (co-authored, 1957), and others. "Materials for the Uzbek Language Course" (co-author).

It is well-known that the dialects of the Uzbek language hold a special position among Turkic languages due to their unique phonetic features and rich vocabulary. Consequently, dialectology is considered one of the most challenging and complex branches of Uzbek linguistics. Classifying these dialects, studying the history of their formation and the linguistic phenomena specific to each dialect through comparative research, and demonstrating the role of dialects in the development of the literary language require deep theoretical knowledge and scientific intuition from the linguist. Sh.Shobdurahmonov is a courageous researcher who has achieved great success by dedicating himself to studying this difficult yet rare source, which brings great scientific honor to the scholar.

Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov began to focus on dialectology primarily from 1955. His work in this field was supported by the scientific assistance of Professor V.V.Reshetov. He actively participated in dialectological expeditions organized under the leadership of A.K.Borovkov and V.V.Reshetov to study and collect material on Uzbek folk dialects. As a result, serious scientific research in this area began to yield results. He became known to the public as the author of several significant articles and monumental works.

In 1963, the scholar defended his doctoral dissertation on the topic "Uzbek Literary Language and Uzbek Folk Dialects (The Issue of Interrelationship between Key Urban Dialects and Modern Uzbek Literary Language)". The main content of the doctoral dissertation was published in 1962 as a separate book under the same title. Official opponents - Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan, Doctor of Philological Sciences Mamed-aga Shiraliyev, renowned scholar and prominent Turkologist, Professor N.A.Baskakov, and Doctors of Philological Sciences G.Abdurahmonov and S.Ibrahimov - highly praised the work of Sh.Shobdurahmonov. In this major study, Shoabdurahmonov examines the Tashkent-Fergana type dialects of the Karluk dialect, a field that had been largely unexplored in linguistics until then. The scholar's doctoral dissertation holds significant scientific-theoretical and practical importance not only for Uzbek linguistics but also for the entire field of Turkology. In this monographic work, the scholar addressed numerous issues including the formation of the Uzbek literary language, the role of folk dialects in shaping the literary language, the Uzbek dialects that form the basis of the literary language and their primary

phonetic, morphological, and lexical features, the role of dialects in defining and standardizing literary language norms, the relationship between dialects that form the foundation of the literary language and other Uzbek dialects, as well as matters of orthography and orthoepy. Additionally, against the backdrop of these issues, the scholar resolved questions such as the emergence of “o” vocalization in the Uzbek language (in both literary language and dialects) and its spread to syllables, the appearance of diphthongs in Uzbek and their disappearance in core dialects, diphthongs and sound combinations, and root structure.

In this work, the scholar’s clear, accurate, and highly valuable conclusion deserves recognition: Tashkent-type dialects are phonetically closer to the literary language, while Fergana-type dialects are morphologically closer. This is because the orthographic and orthoepic norms of the literary language were formed based on Tashkent-type dialects, while morphological norms were established based on Fergana-type dialects. However, in determining the lexical norms of the literary language, not only Tashkent and Fergana dialects but also other Uzbek folk dialects played a role. In summary, this work of the scholar was acknowledged as a highly significant contribution to the field of Uzbek linguistics.

In 1959, Sh. Shoabdurahmonov, together with V.V. Reshetov, wrote the book “Uzbek Dialectology”. This work was later revised, supplemented and published as a complete and unified textbook for higher education institutions in 1962 and 1978. The first textbook on Uzbek dialectology, intended for philological faculties of higher education institutions, remained the main reference for many years.

A number of other scientific works of the scientist also played a significant role in the fact that Uzbek dialectology occupied a significant place among the dialectology of other Turkic languages: “Qo’qon shevasining ba’zi bir fonetik xususiyatlari” (1957), “O’zbek shevalarining leksik sostavini o’rganish masalalari haqida” (1958), “Изучение и задачи узбекской диалектологии” (1958), “Dialektologik kuzatishlardan” (1958), “O’zbek adabiy tilining shevalarga munosabati” (1960), “Shahar shevalari leksikasidan” (1960), “Узбекский литературный язык и его влияние на говоры” (1960), “Undoshlarning o’rin almashishi – metateza” (1961), “Tayanch shahar shevalari leksikasidan” (1961), “Tayanch shahar shevalarning fonetik sistemasi” (1963), “Yetakchi o’zbek shahar shevalarining klassifikatsiyasi masalasi” (1965), “O’zbek tilida o’zak strukturasi ba’zi masalalariga doir” (1965), “Некоторые фонетические особенности ташкентского говора” (1966), “O’zbek shevalarida leksik moslik va ularning adabiy tilga munosabati” (1966), “Leksik dubletlar va ularning adabiy normasini belgilash” (1966), “O’zbek tilining dialektologik atlas” (1969), “O’zbek tili shevalarida geminatlar” (1979), “O’zbek tilida diftonglar” (1981) many of his works, such as the ones in the dialectological section, are examples of scientific research work for dialectological researchers in terms of their dialectological accuracy and correctness, richness of factual material, scientific maturity, correct formulation and clear solution of the problem, and practical significance.

In his articles “Classification of Uzbek Urban Dialects” (1965) and “Dialectological Atlas of the Uzbek Language” (1969), Sh. Shoabdurakhmanov elucidated the classification of the foundational urban dialects that formed the basis of the Uzbek literary language, as well as the issues surrounding the compilation of a dialectological atlas. Under Sh. Shoabdurakhmanov’s leadership and direct participation, materials on Uzbek dialects (facts from 16 locations in Uzbekistan on phonetics, morphology, lexicon, and semasiology) were collected and

transferred to linguistic maps for the fundamental work "Atlas of Turkic Languages". The "Dictionary of Uzbek Folk Dialects", compiled under the leadership and co-authorship of Shonazar Shoabdurakhmanov and published in 1971, can be considered a significant innovation in the dialectal lexicography of that time. The scholar also actively participated in the compilation of the "Dialectological Atlas of Turkic Languages", a major milestone in Turkology. In this project, he headed the "Uzbek Language" section of the atlas, as well as coordinated the work on compiling the atlas for the Central Asian region. Under his leadership and personal involvement, the monograph "Uzbek Dialects of the Tashkent Region" (1977) was published. The work "Morphology of Uzbek Dialects" (1984) was also published. The scholar's major monograph "The Karluk Dialect of the Uzbek Language" (1983) was published in Russian. This work comprehensively analyzes the phonetic, morphological, and lexical features of urban-type dialects belonging to the Karluk dialect, which forms the dialectological basis of the Uzbek literary language.

The distinguished dialectologist, in his research, studied and classified Uzbek folk dialects comprehensively for the first time. He categorized Uzbek dialects into specific types and identified the orthoepic, morphological, and lexical features characteristic of each type. He also determined their role in the formation of the Uzbek literary language.

The scholar also made significant contributions to the field of lexicography. Sh. Shoabdurahmonov, who edited volumes III, IV, and V of the five-volume "Russian-Uzbek Dictionary" (1953-55) and made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek lexicography, is also the author of major scientific research on the phonetics, morphology, and lexicon of the modern Uzbek literary language. In particular, "O'zbek tilida yordamchi so'zlar" (1953), "O'zbek tilida o'zak strukturasi ba'zi masalalariga doir" (1965), "O'zbek tilida yuklamalar" (1971), "O'zbek adabiy tilining leksik normalari" (1973) kabi maqolalari, shuningdek, "Hozirgi zamon o'zbek tili" (1957), "O'zbek tili grammatikasi I jild. Morfologiya" (1975), "Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili" (1980). His co-authored scientific works are distinguished by their comprehensive approach to the issue and the soundness of their theoretical conclusions.

Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov was awarded the academic title of professor in 1967. In 1973, he became a laureate of the Abu Rayhan Beruni State Prize of Uzbekistan, along with a group of scholars from the republic, for his participation in researching and publishing the literary and artistic heritage of the famous folk bakhshi Ergash Jumanbulbul o'g'li (five volumes in Uzbek and three in Russian).

The significant contributions of the renowned scholar in the field of Uzbek philology, particularly Uzbek linguistics, were highly acclaimed. In 1968, he was elected a corresponding member of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, and in 1974, he became the first linguist from the republic to be elected a full member of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan.

In his later years, the scholar worked tirelessly on creating the "Etymological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" and presented the initial results of his research to the scientific community through a series of articles published in the "Etymology" section of the "Uzbek Language and Literature" journal.

Conclusion. Sh. Shoabdurahmonov, as a caring and demanding mentor and a skilled science organizer, has paid great attention to training highly qualified personnel in the field of philology in our country. Under his supervision and especially as an opponent, several

individuals not only from Uzbeks but also from Karakalpak, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Tatar, Azerbaijani, and Uyghur peoples have defended their candidate and doctoral dissertations. Under the direct scientific guidance of the scholar, nearly 30 doctoral and candidate dissertations have been defended. The mentor scholar, who has created major works in all areas of Uzbek linguistics, has served as an opponent for more than 20 doctoral and over 80 candidate dissertations.

Notably, Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov's wife, Maqsuda Sodikova, was also a linguist scholar - a Doctor of Philological Sciences.

His textbooks and manuals on Uzbek dialectology, orthography and punctuation, and modern Uzbek literary language have long been among the main literature for students of philology faculties in higher educational institutions of our country. Shonazar Shoabdurahmonov, one of the hardworking and dedicated representatives of Uzbek philology and a renowned linguist scholar, passed away on October 2, 2011, at the age of 88.

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